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Intellectual Property as An Object of Entrepreneurial Activity

Girişimcilik Faaliyetinin Konusu Olarak Fikri Mülkiyet

ABSTRACT

The article examines the challenges associated with the use of the results of intellectual activity in civil circulation, where intellectual property objects become the subject of various transactions in the course of entrepreneurial activity. It further conceptualizes intellectual property as a synthesized category that encompasses the exclusive rights of its owner to the outcomes of intellectual and creative activity. The article also highlights a distinctive feature of intellectual property rights — their territorial nature — which is linked to the laws of a particular state. The article further notes that with the advancement of technologies for creating and transmitting information, methods of reproduction have expanded significantly.

Keywords: Intellectual property, entrepreneurial activity, exclusive rights, legal protection, territorial nature.

ÖZET

Makale, fikri mülkiyet eserlerinin girişimcilik faaliyeti sırasında çeşitli işlemlerin konusu haline geldiği sivil dolaşımda, bu faaliyet sonuçlarının kullanımıyla ilgili zorlukları incelemektedir. Ayrıca, fikri mülkiyeti, fikri ve yaratıcı faaliyetlerin sonuçlarına ilişkin sahibinin münhasır haklarını kapsayan sentezlenmiş bir kategori olarak kavramsallaştırmaktadır. Bunların yanı sıra, fikri mülkiyet hakkının belirgin bir özelliği olan, belirli bir devletin yasalarıyla bağlantılı bölgesel niteliğini vurgulamaktadır. Makale bilgi oluşturma ve iletme teknolojilerinin gelişmesiyle birlikte, çoğaltma yöntemlerinin önemli ölçüde genişlediğini belirtmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Fikri mülkiyet, girişimcilik faaliyeti, münhasır haklar, hukuki koruma, bölgesel nitelik.

1. INTRODUCTION

The copyright legislation of all developed countries essentially treated these rights as property rights, seeing and protecting primarily the economic essence of the rights. The understanding that not only material but also immaterial rights exist in the sphere of creative works was influenced by the philosophical ideas of I. Kant, who viewed copyright not simply as a type of property belonging to the author or publisher, but also as the focus of certain moral interests of the author, which in modern legislation are referred to as personal non-property rights.

Since Kazakhstan was part of the Soviet Union for a long time, it is necessary to note some specific features of Russian intellectual property legislation. First of all, the legal protection of copyrighted works, technical innovations, and other intellectual property in Russia appeared much later than in Western Europe and the United States. Laws on copyright, patents for inventions, and the protection of trademarks and industrial designs, which were largely in line with the requirements of the time and similar to European models, were only adopted in Russia at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries. The Soviet period once again set Russian intellectual property legislation back a long way, with the result that by the end of the 20th century, before the start of reforms, this area of legislation lagged significantly behind Western European legislation in its development.

Furthermore, a characteristic feature of Russian legislation, which is gradually being overcome, was the traditionally low level of protection of copyright and patent rights. Another specific feature in this area was the extensive state intervention in the relations between the creators of creative achievements and their users.

The establishment and development of legal protection for intellectual property in the Russian Empire followed broadly the same path as that taken by this sub-sector in European countries and the United States, albeit with some differences. Researchers have identified the following features in the field of copyright during that period:

- the dominance of the state monopoly on book printing until the end of the 18th century, manifested in the fact that the first private ('free') printing house appeared only in 1771;
- the granting of privileges by the state only to publishers and the absence of legal relations between publishers and authors as a subject of legal regulation;
- the close connection between Russian copyright and censorship legislation;
- the recognition in the 19th century of copyright as a type of property right and the introduction of the concepts of literary and artistic property;
- the adoption of full copyright in its modern sense only in 1911.

Russian patent law developed in much the same way as European and American patent law. The first patent law in Russia was adopted in 1812. Although Emperor Alexander I's manifesto of 17 June 1812 was called 'On privileges for various inventions and discoveries in the arts and crafts,' the privilege was understood to be a document certifying and protecting the exclusive right to an invention (patent).

On 22 November 1833, during the reign of Emperor Nicholas I, amendments and additions were made to the law by the document 'Provisions on Privileges' prepared by the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Internal Affairs. The provisions introduced important principles and concepts that brought it closer to modern patent laws. For example, Russian and foreign subjects had equal rights when applying for and using privileges. The concept of temporary use of the object of privilege and the entire privilege was also introduced, somewhat reminiscent of modern licence agreements. The provision contains requirements that are familiar from today's legislation: industrial applicability; compliance of the technical solution with the requirements of society; refusal to protect the solution to a problem by non-technical means; and the presence of a detailed description of the invention in the documents for obtaining the privilege.

Subsequent developments in Russian patent law, taking into account progressive changes in European legislation, gradually shifted from understanding privileges as an act of tsarist mercy to recognising the legal right to protect inventions.

Thus, it can be concluded that many provisions in modern legislation concerning intellectual property and its protection are the achievements of legal thought and law enforcement practice in various countries, which took shape during the formation and flourishing of national systems.

In the 19th century, industrialised countries realised that protecting intellectual property at the national level alone was insufficient. For this reason, the internationalisation of intellectual property protection began to develop rapidly. The threat of the actual cancellation of the next international technical exhibition in Vienna in 1873 prompted the start of a long period of work on harmonising national patent systems and creating a global system for the protection of intellectual property. The refusal to participate was justified by fears of losing priority for their inventions due to inadequate legal protection and industrial espionage. To resolve this situation, the Austrian authorities initiated the adoption of a special law providing temporary legal protection for inventions, industrial designs and trademarks of foreigners who presented them at the exhibition (World Intellectual Property Organization, 1883). Subsequently, numerous events and conferences were held on this issue, and relevant documents were adopted. In 1883, representatives of 11 states adopted and signed a convention in Paris, which went down in the history of relations in this field as the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property (World Intellectual Property Organization, 1967).

To complete the picture of this period in the development of global and national legal protection systems for intellectual property, and to properly understand the interrelationship and similarities between national protection systems, it should be noted that similar processes were taking place not only in the field of industrial property. The lack of uniformity and completeness of the legal protection of various works provided by bilateral agreements led to the adoption of the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works on 9 September 1886 (World Intellectual Property Organization, 1886). The official international legal concept and modern system of intellectual property objects were enshrined in the WIPO Convention, signed in Stockholm on 14 July 1967 (World Intellectual Property Organization, 1967). The list

of intellectual property objects given in Article 1 of the Convention formed the basis for their legislative definition in many countries, including the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Consequently, the global history of the evolution of intellectual property law can be divided into three periods. The first period covers the 15th century and the last quarter of the 18th century, and we call it the period of monopoly privileges. The second period lasted from approximately 1790 to 1883 and can be called the period of the heyday of national intellectual property protection systems. The third period can be dated from 1883 and called the period of global conventions.

The beginning of the return of the concepts and legal categories of 'intellectual property,' 'industrial property,' and 'intellectual property rights' should be considered the adoption of the Fundamentals of Civil Legislation of the USSR and the Republics of 31 May 1991 and the USSR Law of 6 March 1990 'On Property in the USSR'.

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the active use of these categories and the targeted regulation of relations concerning them began, perhaps, with the attainment of state sovereignty. Thus, Article 9, 'Private Property of Citizens,' of the Law of the Kazakh SSR of 15 December 1990 'On Property in the Republic of Kazakhstan' states: 'The products of intellectual and material activity are the private property of citizens...'.

Although the categories of 'intellectual property' and 'intellectual property rights' were not used in a positive sense in the legislation of the USSR (except for normative acts from the period preceding its collapse), certain protection was, of course, provided for objects of literary, artistic, technical creative activity and means of individualisation. However, for the vast majority of such objects, such as inventions, utility models, and industrial designs, the exclusive rights to their use belonged not to the authors who created them, but to the state in the form of its various bodies and organisations.

In the most general sense, the essence of the changes in this area after the change in the economic system was expressed in the transfer of exclusive rights to use the achievements of creative activity to private individuals and organisations, as well as the introduction of other attributes of private appropriation and disposal in this sphere.

Meanwhile, regardless of the procedure for using the results of creative activity in the former USSR, objective processes were taking place in the world involving the active establishment of national systems for the protection of intellectual property, internationalisation and globalisation of relations in the scientific, technical and commercial spheres. Naturally, Kazakhstan and other 'new countries' should use the means and methods typical for a certain stage of market development of the state in building their systems, also taking into account the achievements of global integration processes (Republic of Kazakhstan, 1996).

It is also worth mentioning the role and significance of intellectual property, scientific research and the state of legislation in this area at the current stage of Kazakhstan's development. The results of intellectual creative activity are widely used in various spheres of society: industry, art, education, etc. They are particularly important in the context of the development of market relations. The Republic of Kazakhstan is one of the countries that recognise that intellectual property is an integral part of technological, cultural and scientific progress, as well as progress in the field of information services, which, in turn, is the basis for the successful development of the country's economy and the well-being of society. As for the state of legislation, it should be noted that today there is a set of normative legal acts that form the basis for the legal regulation of relations concerning intellectual property objects. Firstly, this is the Civil Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan (hereinafter referred to as the CC RK), which contains the basic provisions on intellectual property rights and certain objects thereof.

Secondly, there are special laws that regulate in more detail the norms relating to specific objects of intellectual property: the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan of 10 June 1996 'On Copyright and Related Rights' (hereinafter referred to as the Copyright Law) (Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Trademarks, Service Marks, and Appellations of Origin of Goods"), the Patent Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated 16 July 1999 (hereinafter referred to as the Patent Law), (Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Protection of Plant Varieties) the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated 26 July 1999 'On Trademarks, Service Marks and Appellations of Origin of Goods' (Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Legal Protection of Topographies of Integrated Circuits), the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated 13 July 1999 'On the Protection of Selection Achievements'(Concept of Intellectual Property Rights Protection), the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated 29 June 2001 'On the Legal Protection of Topologies of Integrated Circuits'(Civil Law. Volume 3. Textbook for Universities (Academic Course) and several other legislative

acts. Various programmes and concepts for the protection of intellectual property rights are also being developed and implemented (World Trade Organization, 1994).

In a relatively short period of time, numerous amendments and additions have been made to the above-mentioned legislative acts. In 2004, fundamental changes were made with regard to industrial property, and in 2005, with regard to copyright and related rights. Due to the rapid pace of development in the field of intellectual property, there is once again a need to amend certain legislative acts.

Despite the centuries-long history of the development of intellectual property law, issues in this field still remain of great interest for scientific research. Intellectual property constitutes the subject of study in many scholarly works. In recent years, numerous academic articles have been written, possessing not only theoretical but also practical significance.

2. THE PROCESS OF INCORPORATING THE RESULTS OF INTELLECTUAL ACTIVITY INTO CIVIL CIRCULATION

Recently, we have been observing a process of the incorporation of the results of intellectual activity into civil turnover, with intellectual property increasingly becoming the subject of various transactions and entrepreneurial activity. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated 22 April 1998, No. 220-I 'On Limited and Additional Liability Partnerships' (as amended and supplemented as of 27 February 2017) in Article 13, which regulates the procedure for establishing a limited liability partnership, in part 3, paragraph 1, states that if the procedure for establishing a limited liability partnership is terminated before its completion, the founders of the partnership who have contributed money, securities, property, property rights, including the right to the results of intellectual activity (our italics), and other property for the formation of the authorised capital, shall be entitled to demand their immediate return (Republic of Kazakhstan, 1998).

In this regard, it seems necessary to consider the peculiarities of such a legal phenomenon as intellectual property, which is understood as a synthesised concept that covers exclusive rights to the results of intellectual, or rather, creative activity (mental, sensory, volitional, etc.) in the fields of science, technology, literature, art, design and the creation of trademarks.

The understanding of intellectual property as an exclusive right is expressed in Article 125 of the Civil Code, which recognises the exclusive right of a citizen or legal entity to the results of intellectual creative activity and means of individualisation of a legal entity, products of a natural or legal entity, works or services performed by them (brand name, trademark, service mark, etc.). The same article establishes that the use of the results of intellectual creative activity and means of individualisation that may be subject to exclusive rights (intellectual property) may be carried out by third parties only with the consent of the right holder (Republic of Kazakhstan, 2011). In other words, the law indicates that the main component of intellectual property rights to a specific object is the exclusive right of its owner.

When considering the issue of intellectual property rights, it is important to define their relationship to property rights in general. Yu.G. Basin, in defining the concept of property rights, notes the need to expand it in modern conditions and to distinguish several types of property rights:

- a) the right to materialised property;
- b) property rights to tangible symbols of things and goods;
- c) property rights to properly recorded current assets without the use of tangible recording media;
- d) intellectual property rights to creative works (with further internal division) (Basin, 2003, p. 28–39).

At the same time, he notes that "property rights as a set of absolute powers of the owner's economic authority over the object belonging to him combines several mutually different groups of powers. Each of these groups, depending on the nature of the object of property rights, has its own characteristics in terms of the content of powers and the methods of their protection. These features are already taken into account by legislation and law enforcement practice. The task of science is to more accurately define the features that unite and divide the corresponding groups of legal relations in order to improve the effectiveness of their legal regulation" (Basin, 2003, p. 28–39).

Professor T.E. Kaudirov also speaks of the need to distinguish between property rights and intellectual property rights, since the latter have fundamental characteristics and distinctive features as objects of civil rights (Kaudyrov, 2001, p. 448). The latter can be illustrated by the peculiarities of the use of copyrighted objects in business activities.

3. FEATURES OF THE EMERGENCE AND PROTECTION OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

The regulation of relations concerning the emergence and protection of intellectual property rights has a number of distinctive features. One of the main features of intellectual property rights is their territorial nature, i.e. they arise in accordance with the laws of a particular state, and their legal protection is limited to its territory. Unlike property rights, intellectual property rights are only recognised in the country of origin. In other countries, these rights are not protected, and a work, invention or means of individualisation may be used by third parties without restriction or will only be protected if there is an international agreement in the form of a bilateral treaty or multilateral convention.

The second distinctive feature is their temporary nature. Thus, while the right to a tangible object arises for the owner and, ideally, is considered to belong to him forever or until he makes a corresponding declaration of intent to dispose of the object, in contrast, the right to intellectual property is valid for a limited period of time.

The third feature of intellectual property rights is their exclusive nature, which manifests itself in the fact that only the right holder has the monopoly (exclusive) right to sell and exploit the object, derive economic benefit, distribute (reproduce) and use it in other ways. All third parties are obliged to recognise property rights and intellectual property rights and not to interfere with the rights holders in their exercise.

Other characteristic features of intellectual property rights as objects of civil rights are:

- intangibility and ideality (immateriality);
- protection of rights in cases strictly established by law;
- a variety of possibilities for protecting rights;
- a specific form of securing rights and the status of ownership of an object.

Thus, intellectual property rights can be defined as a set of absolute, territorially and temporally limited personal non-property and property rights of an exclusive nature to intangible (immaterial and ideal) intellectual property objects that are secured by legislative acts and belong to a subject of civil law. intellectual property objects fixed in a certain way – the results of intellectual creative activity and means of individualisation of subjects and objects of market relations.

4. WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW, A CLEAR DISTINCTION MUST BE DRAWN BETWEEN COPYRIGHT AND NEIGHBORING RIGHTS

Within the framework of intellectual property, a distinction should be made between copyright and related rights. Related rights apply to productions, performances, phonograms, and broadcasts by terrestrial and cable broadcasting organisations, regardless of their purpose, content, and merit, as well as the manner and form of their expression. Accordingly, the subjects of related rights are performers, producers of phonograms, and terrestrial and cable broadcasting organisations, which, in the vast majority of cases, carry out entrepreneurial activities. The very name of these rights – ‘related’ – implies their derivative nature and their connection with the basic rights. Related rights are directly linked to copyright. Performers exercise their rights subject to compliance with the rights of the authors of the works they perform. Producers of phonograms and broadcasting organisations exercise their rights, including in the course of their business activities, within the limits of the rights obtained under agreements with performers and authors of works recorded on phonograms.

The civil legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan understands intellectual property rights primarily as an element of civil legal capacity. This is precisely the meaning of Article 14 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which establishes that, as an essential component of legal capacity, a citizen may have intellectual property rights to inventions, works of science, literature and art, and other results of intellectual activity (Republic of Kazakhstan, 2011). At the same time, a citizen's intellectual property rights may also be the subject of entrepreneurial activity. In this case, entrepreneurial activity may be carried out not only by the author himself, but also by other entities that hold related rights. Let us consider the peculiarities of the

implementation of related rights associated with the right to reproduce a particular copyrighted object. The right to reproduce is the subject of an article by S. Masalina, which fully reveals the essence of these concepts and is entitled 'The Concept of the Right to Reproduce' (Masalina, 2001 pp. 97-147). The article reveals important issues that are of fundamental importance in understanding not only the right to reproduce, but also copyright in general. Let us consider the main provisions of S. Masalina's article as they apply to entrepreneurial activity.

At first glance, the concepts of 'reproduction' and 'right to reproduction' do not seem complicated, but with the development of technology, they are acquiring new qualities and meanings. The example of the right to reproduction illustrates the influence of technological development on copyright.

Since copyright, in simplified terms, is intended to protect the copyright holder from illegal copying of their work, it is logical that historically the first object of copyright (or rather, the prototype of copyright) was the book. However, it was not even the stage when it became possible to simply print a book that was decisive for the emergence of copyright, but the emergence of technology that made it possible to copy books in mass print runs. The invention of the printing press gave birth not only to publishing, but also to counterfeiting. According to researchers, copyright could not have emerged until illegal copying became a profitable business. Therefore, as long as copying was done by hand, illegal copying did not exist, since illegal reproduction would have cost no less than the creation of the original.

5. THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROGRESS IN THE FORMATION AND ADVANCEMENT OF COPYRIGHT LAW

The right of authors to publish their works was first enshrined in law in England in 1710 in the Statute of Queen Anne. Copyright was given the name 'copyright' - 'the right to copies', thereby signifying that the essence of copyright is the author's right to authorise or prohibit the creation of copies of their work (Seignette, 1994, pp.15–26).

From this brief excursion into history, we can already conclude that technological factors influenced the emergence and development of copyright, as evidenced by the need to establish the right to reproduce works with the advent of equipment that could copy them in unlimited quantities. Article 2 of the Copyright Act establishes the following concept of reproduction: "Reproduction is the production of one or more permanent or temporary copies of works or objects of related rights by any means and in any form, in whole or in part, directly or indirectly. The types of reproduction are: the production of sound or video recordings, the production of one or more copies of a two-dimensional or three-dimensional work, as well as any permanent or temporary storage of works or objects of related rights in any material form (Republic of Kazakhstan, 1996).

From this definition, S. Masalina identifies the following elements of reproduction:

- the existence of (any) objective form of the work (which follows from the words 'production of copies in any form');
- the re-giving of an objective form or the giving of a new form to the work (which is confirmed by the phrase 'by any means and in any form, in whole or in part, directly or indirectly');
- for the recognition of the fact of reproduction, it is irrelevant how long the material form is preserved, i.e. how long a copy of the work exists (which follows from the expression 'any permanent or temporary storage of works or objects of related rights in any material form') (Masalina, 2001, p. 113).

With regard to the material form of a copy of a work, it should be borne in mind that there are two fundamental principles in copyright law: copyright in a work arises from the moment of its creation, i.e. from the moment it is fixed on a material object; copyright does not extend to ideas, concepts, principles, methods, systems, processes, discoveries or facts themselves. These principles form the basis of the first element of the right of reproduction. According to E.P. Gavrilov, 'reproduction is considered to have taken place regardless of whether the relevant material objects have become available to an indefinite circle of persons' (Gavrilov, 1984, p.153). A.P. Sergeev cites the possibility of perception of the work by third parties as a criterion of objectivity of form (Sergeev, 2000, 219), i.e., the reproduced work must in principle be possible for users to perceive, but it is not necessary for it to actually become accessible to them.

All attempts to provide an exhaustive list of reproduction methods have ultimately failed, as it is not considered appropriate to reflect these methods in legislation. This is because, with the passage of time and the development of technologies for creating and transmitting information, the concept of 'reproduction' is expanding significantly, and a definition limited to specific methods of reproduction will quickly become obsolete. Dutch professor Bernt Hugenholtz believes that it is only necessary to consistently follow the 'normative' principle inherent in copyright, i.e. to interpret existing rights and exceptions to them not under the influence of new technologies, but in accordance with the purpose of these rights and exceptions (Hugenholtz,1996, p.87).

The identification of such a feature of reproduction as the copying of a work is aimed at differentiating the mechanical process of reproduction from the act of creating a work in the course of the creative process. In this regard, the question arises as to whether reproduction in this case is not simply copying a work in its original form, but rather copying a work that results in its placement in a new objective form (e.g., a building constructed according to an architectural design, a drawing reproducing a photograph, etc.). Soviet legislation did not provide a clear answer to this question, but the prevailing view at the time was that reproduction meant producing a work again in its previous form. In particular, according to O.S. Ioffe: 'Reproduction means multiplying a work by making copies or by any other means' (Ioffe,1969, p.30); reproduction, according to E.P. Gavrilov, 'consists in the right to produce a certain number of copies of a work' (Gavrilov, 1984, p.153). However, today, reproduction should be understood as the re-creation of a work in its original form or in another objective form.

From the above, it can be concluded that the author of a work has the right to authorise or refuse to authorise reproduction, even if the copy of the work finds a second life in a different form, which must be taken into account in business activities so as not to infringe the author's rights.

6. METHODS OF REPRODUCTION AS A MEANS OF EXERCISING AUTHORS' RIGHTS

When studying this issue, it is impossible not to touch upon the problem that arises when the right to reproduce a work is equated with other ways of using it, which must be taken into account in the context of business activities and copyright protection. The confusion arose primarily due to the wording of the legislation. The question arises: are the rights to publish, reproduce, and distribute a work independent or do they form part of a single right? For example, French and Belgian courts have considered the right of reproduction to include distribution. S. Ricketson believes that the reason for the absence of an independent right to distribute lies in the adherence to the principle of copyright, according to which copyright is not identical to the right of ownership of the material object in which the work is expressed; therefore, it would be unfair to grant, as copyright, the right to control the circulation of material media (Ricketson,1987,p.402). However, in order to distinguish between the right of ownership of physical media and copyright, the principle of exhaustion of distribution rights is introduced into the legislation of countries. For example, if copies of a lawfully published work are introduced into civil circulation through their sale, their further distribution is permitted without the author's consent and without payment of remuneration. In order to implement this principle, the right of distribution must be separated into an independent right. If it remains within the scope of the right of reproduction, then with each new transfer of the right of reproduction in relation to the same work, there is a risk that the right of distribution will be transferred again each time, even though it was already exhausted during the first transfer.

In addition, in Soviet civil law science, reproduction or distribution was often confused with public performance. There were claims that the public performance of a literary work constituted distribution or that reproduction also included the public performance of a published work. Today, a different approach prevails, according to which public performance should not be a means of reproduction, but a means of using a work that is distinct from it. Even in the 1991 Fundamentals of Civil Legislation (OGZ), the approach to reproduction was still conceptually ambiguous. Reproduction was understood to include publication, public performance, broadcasting, cable television, satellite television, as well as video and sound recording. It follows that by granting the right of reproduction, the author thereby transfers all of the rights listed above.

However, current legislation treats each right as separate and stipulates the obligation to obtain permission from the author or other rights holder for any use of the work and, accordingly, to pay remuneration for each transferred right, as enshrined in paragraph 5 of Article 16 of the Copyright Law (Masalina,2001,pp.122-124). The latter means that, when interpreting the provisions of current legislation, it should be borne in mind that only those rights that are expressly specified in the contract are considered to be transferred author's rights.

Throughout the 19th and 20th centuries, technical devices such as cameras, satellites, radio, television, computers, audio and video equipment, photocopiers, modems and scanners were invented. All of them have influenced the emergence of new ways of using works, in other words, the expansion of copyright. In such circumstances, subparagraph 11 of paragraph 2 of Article 16, introduced into the Law on 9 July 2004, becomes even more important. according to which the author or other copyright holder has the right to perform other actions not listed in the Law, if they do not contradict the legislative acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan, and accordingly, the author or other copyright holder has the right to remuneration for each type of use of the work. Thus, the advent of the Internet has demonstrated that "the right to reproduction in a "digital environment" is a very unreliable right (Leontiev,2005,p.6). It does not provide the owner of copyright and related rights with the possibility of reliable control over the use of objects belonging to him. That is why at the international level – in the WIPO (World Intellectual Property Organisation) of 20 December 1996 on copyright and on performances and phonograms – enshrined the 'right to make available to the public' in order to give authors the opportunity to control the use of their works on the Internet.

7. REPRODUCTION OF TEMPORARY AND PERMANENT COPIES OF A WORK.

A few words should be said about the reproduction of temporary and permanent copies of a work. There are no difficulties with permanent copies, but when it comes to temporary copies, some questions arise. When working on a computer, temporary copies of the files with which the user is working are created in the computer's memory. Since files may contain objects of copyright and related rights, their unauthorised reproduction on users' computers infringes the rights of authors and holders of related rights. At the same time, it would be unreasonable and practically impossible to obtain the consent of the copyright holder for such temporary reproduction. According to S. Masalina, the purpose of including temporary reproduction in the concept of 'reproduction' is to demonstrate that temporary reproduction is also covered by the cases of free use of a work provided for by the Law, and therefore right holders cannot claim either that they be asked for permission or that they receive remuneration for temporary copies in cases where this is not justified. In other words, the purpose of including temporary reproduction in the concept of reproduction is to protect the interests of users, including entrepreneurs, rather than those of rights holders (Masalina, 2001, p.126).

Thus, an analysis of the main provisions of the legislation and the theoretical positions expressed by scholars in their works leads to the conclusion that the concepts of 'reproduction' and 'right to reproduce' are diverse in content and have not found an unambiguous definition. It is necessary to precisely define in law the characteristics and elements inherent in reproduction within the framework of copyright and related rights, allowing it to be distinguished from other ways of using a work, as this is of practical importance for the proper organisation of business activities related to the use of intellectual property.

State policy in the field of intellectual property rights protection is the link between the creation of works and other results of intellectual activity and their use in business activities.

8. STATE POLICY IN THE FIELD OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS PROTECTION

At the same time, the system for protecting these rights should not create an overly cumbersome legal framework of protective measures, which could hinder the use of intellectual property, but should contribute to the solution of such tasks as:

Strengthening the scientific and technical potential of the republic, stimulating creative activity;

Developing and using new technologies, producing competitive products;

Creating conditions for the development of innovative activity;

Creating conditions for domestic and international exchange of new equipment and technologies, forming a market for scientific and technical products; creating conditions that encourage fair competition,

Protecting the domestic market from counterfeit goods, supporting domestic producers of goods and services;

Creating a favourable investment climate and attracting investment in knowledge-intensive and high-tech industries;

Developing and disseminating information about new achievements and developments.

9. CONCLUSION

As can be seen from the above, the Civil Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan contains provisions aimed at regulating and protecting intangible assets, which differ significantly from the previous civil legislation. While the earlier Civil Code provided rules on the protection of specific personal rights of citizens and legal entities, the currently effective Code establishes rules common to all personal non-property rights and other intangible assets regarding their regulation and protection. Thus, it is evident that the regulation and protection of intangible assets are carried out comprehensively, through the norms of several branches of law.

Previously, in civil law, there were two viewpoints concerning the subject of civil-law regulation of relations related to intangible assets and associated personal non-property rights. For example, one group of scholars argued that civil law does not regulate but merely protects personal non-property rights, whereas others asserted that legal regulation and protection of rights cannot be opposed to each other, since regulation implies protection, and protection is exercised through the regulation of the corresponding relations. In recent years, the prevailing view in civil law scholarship has become that civil law not only regulates but also protects intangible assets.

From the analyzed material, it is evident that intangible assets, which include intellectual property objects, are regarded in the Civil Code as a type of object with respect to which civil-law relations may arise. The provision that the Civil Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan provides only an illustrative list of intangible assets enjoying civil-law protection allows the conclusion that even intangible assets not explicitly mentioned in the Code may become objects of civil-law relations.

The peculiarity of exercising non-property rights lies in the fact that the law does not define the limits of the realization of intangible rights and assets by the entitled person, but rather establishes the boundaries of intrusion by third parties into the personal sphere. If these boundaries are violated, the application of coercive measures to restore them is permitted. In determining the limits of conduct of the entitled and obligated persons, moral norms acquire significant importance.

Summing up the work carried out in studying the legal and theoretical foundations of intellectual property, it should be noted that intellectual property has been known to humanity since ancient times, albeit in a different understanding, and continues to attract interest today, being the subject of many scientific studies. In characterizing the concept of “intellectual property right,” it should be emphasized, first, that intellectual property is not the material object itself; moreover, it is generally considered that an intellectual property right is not a property right in the traditional sense with the triad of powers—possession, use, and disposal. Rather, its content consists of exclusive rights to the results of intellectual creative activity.

Intellectual property has certain features and characteristics, including ideality and incorporeality, the protectability of rights in cases expressly provided by law, a variety of means for protecting rights, a specific form of rights fixation and the state of appropriation of the object, as well as territorial, temporal, and exclusive character.

Secondly, regarding the objects of intellectual property rights, there exist numerous opinions. This is particularly evident when considering the issue of classifying the objects of intellectual property rights. We adhere to the position that intellectual property consists of objects of copyright and related rights, as well as industrial property.

In studying copyright and related rights, one can observe imperfections in the legislative norms, not only in specialized provisions but also in general ones, which creates certain practical difficulties. This can be explained by the intensive development of relations in the field of intellectual property, the need for fuller integration of the results of intellectual activity into civil circulation, and so forth. Consequently, all of this leads to a discrepancy between legislation and the actual relations developing in society.

It should also be noted that scientific and technological achievements exert influence, which likewise necessitates amendments to various normative acts. Certain contentious issues also arise in the study of industrial property objects, since approaches and positions of many authors on this matter are ambiguous.

Thirdly, regarding the protection of intellectual property rights, shortcomings are observed in the system of safeguarding and in the mechanism for protecting intellectual property objects. Primarily, this is due to the uncoordinated work of the authorities responsible for ensuring the protection of intellectual property rights, as well as gaps in legislation. The system of intellectual property protection has now become an integral part of the national infrastructure. There are ample grounds to believe that the twenty-first century will become

the era of the intellectual economy, in the development of which creative activity and a reliable system of its legal protection will play a key role. It should be noted that the protection of intellectual property today is a strategically important component of the successful functioning of any business.

In the modern world, intellectual property serves as a tool for technological progress, economic growth, and the creation of material wealth. We regard intellectual property as an increasingly effective means contributing to the development and enhancement of the economic potential of enterprises, particularly in terms of the optimal use of its objects for their commercial development. When discussing intellectual property objects, one of the principal issues is the question of the exclusive right to them. The term “exclusive right” is applied in the intellectual property legislation of most modern countries, as well as in documents of specialized international organizations. Article 964 of the Civil Code defines the exclusive right as a property right of the holder to use an intellectual property object in any manner at their discretion. The use of an object of exclusive rights by other persons is permitted only with the consent of the rights holder.

From the content of the articles of the Civil Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the provisions of specialized laws, it is evident that the exclusive right:

- applies to each and every object of intellectual property rights;
- contains norms of both positive and negative legal regulation;
- unites heterogeneous groups of results of creative activity and means of individualization into a single category of intellectual property objects (Suleimenov& Basin,2004)

An interpretation of the legislative provisions on the exclusive right allows one to assert the presence of two elements in this construct, the interaction of which ensures both the exercise and the protection of this right. From the content of Article 964 of the Civil Code, one can clearly distinguish a right belonging to the holder of the exclusive right and a rule of conduct pertaining to third parties. The right “to use an intellectual property object in any manner at one’s discretion” constitutes the positive element of the exclusive right. The rule establishing that the use of an object of exclusive rights by other persons is permitted only with the consent of the rights holder constitutes the negative element of the exclusive right.

The main characteristic of the exclusive right, coinciding with the analogous characteristic of property rights, is its absolute nature. Another characteristic is its proprietary (economic) nature, which is fully harmonized with the provision of Article 115 of the Civil Code, which classifies the objectified results of creative intellectual activity as property assets and rights. This approach removes any question regarding the degree or level of absoluteness of the rights of holders of intellectual property objects—their rights are absolute by analogy with the rights of owners.

The exclusive right possesses a number of other properties and characteristics that define it specifically as a special legal construct, designed to establish a particular legal regime for intellectual property objects:

- a) Independence from ownership of the material carrier. For example, rights to the SONY trademark exist independently of ownership of equipment bearing the same brand;
- b) The possibility of arising based on a presumption of rights. This characteristic means that, for certain types of objects, the law grants a specific subject the exclusive right without certainty about its actual existence. For example, under Article 9 of the Copyright Law, a person designated as the author on an original or copy of a work is considered the author until evidence to the contrary emerges; preliminary patents for inventions and industrial designs, as well as utility model patents, are granted without verification of compliance with patentability requirements, at the risk and responsibility of the applicant (Articles 21–24 of the Patent Law);
- c) Term-limited nature of the exclusive right. For instance, Article 969 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan establishes that the exclusive right to intellectual property objects is valid for the term provided by the Civil Code or other law. Legislative acts may allow the extension of such a term. Personal non-property rights to the results of intellectual activity, however, are perpetual;
- d) Territorially limited nature of the exclusive right, which means that the exclusive right is valid only within the territory of a specific country;
- e) Monopolistic nature and susceptibility to lawful limitations. This is manifested primarily in the temporal and spatial limitation of exclusive rights and reflects the fact that while the object of an intellectual property exclusive right satisfies the proprietary interests of a specific individual, it simultaneously restricts the creative freedom of third parties in a particular field of art, science, technology, or commerce;

f) Numerous exceptions to the proclaimed rights. Such exceptions are particularly numerous in the Copyright and Related Rights Law. They are encompassed by the term “free use of works” and are aimed at ensuring access to the information and knowledge contained in works.

It can be concluded that the exclusive right to an intellectual property object is:

- Established by legislative acts and encompassing specific subjective rights not related to ownership of a material object;
- An absolute and exclusive right with statutory exceptions, limited in time and territory;
- Enforceable under the threat of state coercion or annulment of the right;
- A proprietary right of the entitled person to use the object in any manner at their discretion and to dispose of it.

The holder of an exclusive right to the results of intellectual creative activity has the ability to grant it to other persons. This is evidenced by the presence in legislation of constructs such as the license agreement and the agreement on the creation and use of the results of intellectual creative activity. According to Article 966 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, under a license agreement, the party holding the exclusive right to a result of intellectual creative activity or to a means of individualization (the licensor) grants the other party (the licensee) the right to temporarily use the relevant intellectual property object in a specified manner. The license agreement is presumed to be remunerated. A license may be either simple (non-exclusive) or exclusive, depending on the rights granted under the license agreement.

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